

MORPHEME ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract. Morphology is the study of words. Morphemes are the minimal units of words that have a meaning and can not be subdivided further. There are two main types: free and bound. Morpheme is article includes a list of references, but its sources remain unclear because it has insufficient. Therefore the researchers conducted the research about morpheme. The research method that was used is descriptive qualitative method. To gain the data the researchers used literature review in which the data gained from dictionary. Every morpheme can be classified as either free or bound. Bound morphemes can be further classified as derivational or inflectional. These categories are mutually exclusive, and as such, a given morpheme will belong to exactly one of them. Free morphemes can function independently as words. Bound morphemes appear only as part of words, always in conjunction with a root and sometimes with other bound morphemes.

Keywords: linguistic, classification of morpheme, derivational, inflectional, free and bound.

1. INTRODUCTION

There are many definitions of morphology given by experts. Aronoff (1994: 12) quotes the opinion of Bloomfield (1993: 207): "Morphologically a language we mean is a construction in which forms or words are bound, but never phrases. Thus, we can say that morphology includes the construction of words and parts of words, "Notions of morphology written earlier, morphology is the science or research that results in the formation or internal structure of words. This formation will produce formations or morpheme, but not phrase. Thus morphology which discusses the structure / construction / part of morpheme in the end tells us we type of types of mm or Tomori (1982: 21) defines morphology as: ". ..the study of word structure - the study of the rules governing the formation of words in language." Articles on morpheme and morpheme formation, while in a broad sense the focus of the

research is the problem of morphology. Morphology of morphological visitors. Morpheme is a priority unit in the analysis

From the description above, it can be seen the complexity in the morphology of the English language, especially in terms of the formation of the adjective word class. The settings are of interest to the author to discuss them further. The things in question are the difficulty of formation of morphemes in derivation, especially in the formation of the adjective word class. The choice of on a adjective word class and not a noun or verb or adverbial is because the adjective has a very important role in changing the meaning of nouns and indirectly changing or differentiating sentence meanings.

Burling (1992: 38) divides morphemes into two namely free morphemes and bound morphemes. The understanding of free morpheme and bound morpheme according to Burling (1992: 38) as follows:

"Morphemes that can stand alone as words are called free morphemes. Those that must be attached to something else are called bound morphemes. In the examples just given, go, walk, boy, mean, flap, and fresh are free morphemes. -ing, -ed, -s, -ful, un-, -abil-, -ity, re-, and -ly are bound morphemes."

a. Bound Morphem

According to Richards (1985: 31), bound morpheme is a linguistic form (a morpheme) which is never used alone but must be used with another morpheme, for example as an affix or combining form. Example: -al, -ful, -less, -ed, -able, -al. So, from Richards's opinion the writer concludes that bound morpheme is the smallest element or the most basic unit in grammar that cannot be subdivided into grammar that cannot be subdivided into even the smallest sense that cannot stand alone.

b. Free Morpheme

According to Richards (1985: 31), a form which can be used in its own is called a free form. Example: Betty, horse, red, write, love, drive. So, from Richards' opinion, the writer concludes that free morpheme is the smallest element or the most basic unit in grammar that cannot be divided into even the smallest sense that can stand alone

2. METHODOLOGY OF THE RESEARCH

In a study required appropriate steps so that there search objectives that have been determined can be agreed. The method is a method needed by researchers to arrive at there search objectives (Alwasilah, 2009: 85). The research method gives what direction and how the research is carried out, the procedures that are taken, the data sources used, and how this data is collected

and analyzed. The method used in this research is descriptive method. Descriptive research is research conducted to evaluate, describe a phenomenon that is happening today by using scientific procedures to answer problems in general.

Actual (Sutedi, 2009: 58). This research uses descriptive method using qualitative. The author tries to describe, contrast, analyze, and interpret the changes that occur in the morphological process of the two languages based on the theory, data, and literature collected. The purpose of this research is to find similarities and differences in phoneme changes in Japanese and Indonesian in morphological processes (affixation, reduplication, composition) in terms of morphophonemic aspects. Therefore, this study is a qualitative study with descriptive contrastive analysis. Bogdan and Taylor in Moleong (2001) revealed that it was qualitative descriptive data in the form of written words or lists of people and observable behavior.

In addition to descriptive methods, this research also uses the method of library (library research), which is the study of literature or the collection of data and information sourced from library books that are related to changes in vocal phonemes and consonants in language.

A. Classification of Morphemes

a) Free and bound morphemes

Every morpheme can be classified as either free or bound. These categories are mutually exclusive, and as such, a given morpheme will belong to exactly one of them. Free morphemes can function independently as words (e.g. town, dog) and can appear within lexemes (e.g. townhall, doghouse). Bound morphemes appear only as parts of words, always in conjunction with a root and sometimes with other bound morpheme.

For example, unappears only accompanied by other morphemes to form a word. Most bound morphemes in English are affixes, particularly prefixes and suffixes. Examples of suffixes are -tion, -ation, -ible, -ing, etc. Bound morphemes that are not affixed are called cranberry morphemes.

Example: girl, system, desire, hope, act, phone, happy.

Bound morphemes are meaning-bearing unit of language, such as prefixes and suffixes, that are attached to unbound morphemes. They can not stand alone. "Their attachment modifies the unbound morphemes in such things as number or syntactic category. For example: Adding the bound morpheme (s) to the unbound morpheme (cat) changes the noun's number

the addition of the (ed) to (augh) changestense. Similarly, the addition of (er) to (run) changes the verb to a noun."

Linguistics recognizes two classes of bound morphemes.

a. The first classis called inflectional morphemes and their influenceon a base word is predictable. Inflectional morphemes modify the grammatical class of words by signalling a change in number, person, gender, tense, and soon, but they do not shift the base form into an other word class. When 'house' becomes 'houses,' it is still a noun even though you have added the plural morphemes.

b. The second class of morphemes is derivational morphemes. They modify a word according to its lexical and grammatical class. They result in more pro found changes on base words. The word 'style' is a noun, butif I makeit 'stylish,' then it is an adjective. In English, derivational morphemes include suffixes (e.g., 'ish,' 'ous,' 'er,' 'y,' 'ate,' and 'able') and prefixes (e.g., 'un,' 'im,"re,' and 'ex')."

B. Classification of bound morphemes

Bound morphemes can be further classified as derivational or inflectional.

a. Derivational morphemes

Derivational morphemes, when combined with a root, change either .The semantic meaning or part of speech of the affected word. For example, in the word happiness,the addition of the bound morpheme-ness to the root happy changes the word from an adjective (happy) to a noun (happiness). In the word unkind, un- functions as a derivational morpheme, for it inverts the meaning of the word for med by the root kind. Generally, the affixes used with a root word are bound morphemes. However, other morphemes such as affixes can be attached to it.

Types of Declines

The various derivations in the speech section are as follows. Derivation of nouns, for example: legitimacy, kindness, and development. Adjective derivation, for example: silk, life, and fragility. Derivation of verbs, example: streng then and blink.

Adverb derivation, for example: along, close, and slow. Examples of Decreases between Talk Parts Word "Inform" (verb)

Information (noun), by giving the suffix -> -ation

Informative (Adjective), by giving suffix -> -ative

Informative (Adverb), by giving suffix -> -ativeand -ly

The word "active" (adjective)

Activate (Verb), by giving the suffix -> -ate

Activation (noun), by giving suffix -> -action

Active (Adverb), by giving the suffix -> -ly

verb to verb: appoint → disappoint

noun to noun: brother → brotherhood

adjective to adjective: practical → impractical

verb to noun: preserve → preservation

verb to adjective: bore → boring

noun to verb: code → codify

noun to adjective: nature → natural

adjective to noun: ugly → ugliness

adjective to verb: soft → soften

adjective to adverb: slow → slowly

b. Inflectional morphemes

Inflectional morphemes modify a verb's tense, aspect, mood, person, or number, or a noun's, pronoun's or adjective's number, gender or case, without affecting the word's meaning or class (part of speech). Examples of applying inflectional morphemes to words are adding -s to the root dog to form dog and adding -ed to wait to form waited. An inflectional morpheme changes the form of a word.

DISCUSSION

A. Inflectional in to noun

Most countable nouns in English have two word forms; a singular and plural. A singular form like cat, consisting of just one morpheme and a plural form like cats, consisting of a root cat and the suffix -s.

There are also so many uncountable nouns that express their plural with no suffix at all. Example (teeth, men, feet, mice) where there is a change in the vowel of the root. However, there are also some whose plurals display not even a vowel change. For example, sheep, fish, deer, those. The conclusion is addition of inflectional suffix -s/-es to noun causes nouns meaning plural.

2. Possessions

Example : that man's bicycle

John's book

John and Mary's house

- Inflectional into verb

Consider the following examples:

- Read + s (third person singular present tense).

- Load + ed (past tense).
- See + en (perfect or passive participle).
- Drink + ing (progressive participle).

a. Inflectional suffixes include :

- -ed/-d past tense
- -ing progressive/continuous
- -en/-t past participle
- -s plural
- 's generative
- -er comparative
- -est superlative

b. Inflectional affixes of verb -Third Singular verb marker

Example : I am sleeping.

She is studying.

The old man walks in the road side.

The cat looks at the mouse.

B. Zero morphemes/null morphemes Generally, these types of morphemes have no visible changes. For instance, the singular form of sheep is "sheep" and its plural is also "sheep". The intended meaning is thus derived from the co-occurring determiner (e.g. in this case "some-" or "a-").

There are several kinds of zeros :

A zero morph, consisting of no phonetic form, is an allo-morph of a morpheme that is otherwise realized in speech. In the phrase two sheep- \emptyset , the plural marker is a zero morph, which is an allo-morph of -s as in two cows. In the phrase I like- \emptyset it, the verb conjugation has a zero affix, as opposed to the third person singular present -s in he likes it.

A zero pronoun occurs in some languages. In the English sentence nobody knows the zero pronoun plays the role of the object to the verb, and in makes no difference it plays the role of the subject. Like wise, the zero pronoun in the book \emptyset I am reading plays the role of the relative pronoun that in the book that I am reading.

This is also referred to as PRO. In pronoun-dropping languages, including null subject languages such as most Romance languages, the zero pronoun is a prominent feature.

A zero subordinate conjunction occurs in English in sentences like I know \emptyset he likes me, in which the zero conjunction plays the role of the subordinate conjunction that in I know that he likes me.

A zero article is an unrealized indefinite or definite article in some languages.

A zero copula, in which a copula such as the verb to be is implied but absent. For example, in Russian the copula is usually omitted in the present tense, as in "Она красивая" (literally: She beautiful), the same happening with colloquial Brazilian Portuguese, as in "irônicos, aqueles" (literally: ironic, those [guys]), though never with the head adjective coming after the subject as usual in Romance languages. In English the copula is sometimes omitted in some non-standard dialects.

examples

cat = cat + $-\emptyset$ = ROOT ("cat") + SINGULAR

cats = cat + -s = ROOT ("cat") + PLURAL

In addition, there are some cases in English where a null morpheme indicates plurality in nouns that take on irregular plurals.

sheep = sheep + $-\emptyset$ = ROOT ("sheep") + SINGULAR

Also, a null morpheme marks the present tense of verbs in all forms but the third person singular:

(I) run = run + $-\emptyset$ = ROOT ("run") + PRESENT: Non-3rd-SINGULAR

4.CONCLUSION

Morpheme is a word that includes a list of references, but its sources remain unclear because it has insufficient meaning. When a morpheme stands by itself, it is considered as a root because it has a meaning of its own (e.g. the morpheme cat) and when it depends on another morpheme to express an idea, it is an affix because it has a grammatical function (e.g. the -s in cats to indicate that it is plural).

Every morpheme can be classified as either free or bound. These categories are mutually exclusive, and as such, a given morpheme will belong to exactly one of them. Free morphemes can function independently as words. Bound morphemes appear only as parts of words, always in conjunction with a root and sometimes without other bound morphemes. Inflection (inflectional) is the process of forming new words by adding affixes to a word that does not change the class of words. In other words, Derivation is the process of affixing a syllable which results in changing the class of words, for example the affix on the word "sing" to "singer". However, the meaning of the two words differs greatly in contrast from "good" to "not good". So that the process enters into the process of derivation, not

inflection even though the word class changes are still the same, namely adjectives in to adjectives.

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